

Is Making a Major Influence?

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Abstract

At many universities, freshman students enter the college of engineering before declaring a specific field of study. In these cases, it is common for each engineering department to offer their own introductory-level class, to both inform and solicit engineers to select their program. Since multiple departments share the same pool of students, a department aiming for good enrollment numbers would find it advantageous to know what about the class influences the selection of that major. To gain insight on the matter, this paper considers the perspective of students enrolled in the Fundamentals of Mechanical Engineering at Carnegie Mellon University. This course implemented two modes of instruction, textbook-based fundamentals in lecture and hands-on modern making activities in laboratory. Before starting the course, students were asked to rate the likelihood that this course would influence their decision to pursue MechE. Additionally, the students were asked to rate the likelihood of pursuing MechE before starting and after completing the course. The response of each student was compared in the pre-course and post-course survey, for which results indicate that a combination of both lecture and laboratory was important to the students' final decision.

Introduction

For many college freshman, their first-year experience includes gathering information about their field of study. For those enrolled in a college of engineering, freshman students were either initially admitted to a specific department before arriving or conduct a process to declare a major after arriving to campus. Since many engineering departments offer a freshman-level course that introduces topics of that field, those courses can be used by students to reaffirm or reconsider their major selection.

At Carnegie Mellon University (CMU), the freshman class of engineering students that entered in the Fall 2024 semester underwent a process to declare their major in the Spring 2025 semester. Each freshman student is required to take two of these introductory courses, one of which is offered by the department that students declare as their major. For the Mechanical Engineering (MechE) Department, the current freshmen-level course introduces them to the three core areas of solid-mechanics, thermal-fluids, and dynamics-controls. This course provides a survey of these three areas through textbook-based fundamentals in lecture twice a week and modern making skills in laboratory once a week. Lectures give weekly homework assignments to implement new knowledge and prepare for tests. The laboratory teaches

modern making skills, which include CAD modeling with SolidWorks parametric software, 3D printing with Creality Ender 3 machines, laser cutting-engraving with Epilog FusionPro48 machines, and physical computing with Arduino platform. For the 2024-2025 academic year, traditional power tools were included as well to quickly produce the framework for a durable prototype. Throughout the course, students apply this training individually to a 1-week duration hands-on challenge for each of the three areas of MechE. At the end of the course, students work in groups on a multi-week duration project building a functional prototype.

The freshman engineering students enrolled in 24-101 Fundamentals of Mechanical Engineering may have selected this course for various reasons. These motivations include but are not limited to the student:

- intending to declare MechE as their major;
- fulfilling their curiosity as to whether MechE is a better fit than their intended major;
- taking an interest in the course activities conducted by MechE, despite being disinterested in pursuing MechE as a major;
- having a belief that MechE will be the least unpleasant course of the limited options for meeting the two course requirement;
- and so on...

This paper will consider freshman students enrolled in an introductory mechanical engineering course. The investigation will search for a relation between students' self-confidence in utilizing modern making skills and intention to declare mechanical engineering as their major. This work aims to answer the question "Is there a connection between conducting modern making activities and declaring MechE as a major?"

Related Work

Introductory engineering courses are prevalent among undergraduate institutions in the United States (US). A prior review of 390 US undergraduate institutions with ABET EAC-accredited engineering programs determined that 76% of them had some requirement for this type of coursework [1]. Due to the ubiquity of having first year engineering school students enrolling in at least one introductory engineering course, several studies have sought the influence of these courses on students' major selection. This body of research has assessed a broad range of factors, such as the institution's

enrollment size and public vs. private status [2], faculty presentations vs. industry panels [3], job prospects and potential for societal contributions [4], decision prior to university enrollment [5], and much more [6]. As time goes by, it is more common for these introduction to engineering classes to include hands-on fabrication and prototyping skills [7], [8], [9].

Higher education has had a proliferation of makerspaces in order to emphasize prototyping among the student populace, particularly in senior capstone courses of engineering to meet ABET standards [10], [11], [12]. These Bachelor's of Science degree-granting programs require students develop prototypes to act as a proof-of-concept of their technical designs. The benefit of this model is allowing engineering students to work on real-world problems in an educational environment.

In order for students to build a prototype, they must first know how to fabricate. In general, students are utilizing more contemporary methods, which have been referred to as modern making skills. These skills encompass modern CAD modeling, 3D printing, laser cutting-engraving, and physical computing. The foundation for analyzing students' abilities to utilize modern making skills was presented at ISAM 2023 by the paper Evaluating the Impact of Training and Applying Modern Making Skills on Students' Self-Assessed Confidence and Improvement [13]. This prior presentation outlined a method for comparing data between a pre-course and post-course survey of students enrolled in 24-101 Fundamentals of Mechanical Engineering (same course as the current study). That prior study focused on assessing students' self-confidence using modern making skills. It included a process of mapping a 5-point Likert scale to numerical values. Following that analysis, the prior work compared each students' change in confidence utilizing modern making skills from the beginning and end of the course responses. The groundwork laid by that prior study allows the current work to investigate a potential connection between modern making skills and declaration of MechE as the students' major.

Methods

This study uses data collected from surveying students in the 24-101 Fundamentals of Mechanical Engineering course at CMU during the fall semester of 2024. On the first day of class, prior to beginning instruction, students were presented with a pre-course survey electronically. Training students in modern making skills was distributed throughout the course. This training was a blend of both online instruction via Pre-Lab assignment and in-person instruction at laboratory. Students applied this training in CAD modeling, 3D printing, laser cutting, and physical computing towards 2 of 3 individual challenges to achieve a task, as well as 1 group project to build a machine. During the last week of the semester, students were presented with a post-course survey electronically. The results of this study was based on 124 of the 153 students enrolled (81%), as these students responded to both the pre-course and post-course survey. Any data from

students that responded to only 1 of the 2 surveys was excluded from this paper.

Consistent with prior work [13], both the pre-course and post-course surveys asked students about their confidence level in utilizing each of the modern making skills. These questions had a multiple-choice answer, which was set up using a 5-point Likert scale. As consistent with prior work, these responses were mapped to numeric values when processing the data in order to view results:

- 1 – “not at all confident”
- 2 – “not so confident”
- 3 – “somewhat confident”
- 4 – “very confident”
- 5 – “extremely confident”

Those values were used in this study to define:

- 1-2 – “low” confidence
- 3 – “neutral” confidence
- 4-5 – “high” confidence

The pre-course and post-course surveys both asked “At this moment, identify the likelihood that you will pursue a Bachelor's Degree in Mechanical Engineering.” This question offered respondents a multiple-choice answer, which was developed using a 5-point Likert scale. During data processing, these responses were mapped to numeric values:

- 1 – “not at all likely”
- 2 – “not so likely”
- 3 – “somewhat likely”
- 4 – “very likely”
- 5 – “extremely likely”

Those values were used in this study to define:

- 1-2 – “low” likelihood
- 3 – “neutral” likelihood
- 4-5 – “high” likelihood

In only the post-course survey, students were asked to consider a statement. “Reflecting on the course, identify the significance of lecture material on your selection of a major (home department: CEE, ChemE, ECE, MechE, or MSE).” Following this, a nearly identical question asked “Reflecting on the course, identify the significance of laboratory material on your selection of a major (home department: CEE, ChemE, ECE, MechE, or MSE).” Both of these questions offered respondents a multiple-choice answer, which was set up using a 5-point Likert scale. In order to process this data, these responses were mapped to numeric values:

- 1 – “not at all important (this information did not change my selected major)”
- 2 – “not so important (this information may not have changed my selected major)”
- 3 – “somewhat important (this information may or may not have influenced my selected major)”
- 4 – “very important (this information may have help me select between 2+ majors)”
- 5 – “extremely important (this information helped me select between 2+ majors)”

Those values were used in this study to define:

- 1-2 – “low” importance
- 3 – “neutral” importance
- 4-5 – “high” importance

The numeric values mapped from responses allowed these three cases to be observed:

- a) Lecture was of higher importance (# for lecture > # for laboratory)
- b) Laboratory was of higher importance (# for lecture < # for laboratory)
- c) Both lecture & laboratory were equally important (# for lecture = # for laboratory)

These two reflection questions were used to compare the influence of lecture vs. laboratory on each student’s likelihood of declaring MechE as a major. When the numerical value (1-5) was higher for lecture and lower for laboratory, lecture was recorded as most influential. Conversely, when the numerical value (1-5) was higher for laboratory and lower for lecture, the data was recorded as laboratory being the most influential. In the case of lecture and laboratory having the same numerical value, it was recorded as both being influential.

Results & Discussion

The Fall 2024 semester, freshman engineering students enrolled in course 24-101 Fundamentals of Mechanical Engineering course at CMU were presented with both the pre-course and post-course survey. At the beginning of the semester, many students affirmed that taking this course would influence their decision on whether to declare MechE as their major. As shown in **Figure 1**, the majority student respondents (65%, n=81) expressed a high likelihood (responded “very likely” or “extremely likely”) to have their decision influenced by taking the course.

Figure 1: The likelihood of the course influencing each student’s decision to declare MechE as their major. This question was only asked in the pre-course survey.

As prior studies have shown, there are factors affecting major selection beyond the expected influence of the course. The most important of which is likely a student’s preexisting

inclination to pursue a particular major [2], [5], [6]. The results in **Figure 2** were used to identify that at the beginning of the course, the majority student respondents (67%, n=83) reported having a high likelihood of pursuing MechE as a major. Interestingly, at the end of the course, the same number of student respondents (67%, n=83) reported having a high likelihood of pursuing MechE as a major. Since the high likelihood number consists of both “very likely” and “extremely likely” responses, it is noteworthy that many student respondents transitioned from “very likely” in the pre-course survey to “extremely likely” in the post-course survey. This stands out in comparison to neutral likelihood and low likelihood responses, which had nearly the same number of students selecting these responses between the pre-course and post-course survey.

Figure 2: The likelihood of each student declaring MechE as their major from the pre-course and post-course survey.

Throughout the semester, students conducted textbook-based fundamentals in lecture twice a week and hands-on modern making activities in laboratory once a week. The training of modern making skills was conducted as a combination of both online instruction via Pre-Lab assignment and in-person instruction at laboratory. Activities guided students to build their modern making skills in the areas of CAD modeling, 3D printing, laser cutting-engraving, and physical computing. At the end of the course, students were asked to rate their confidence in conducting simple tasks for each of the modern making skills [13]. The confidence responses (high, neutral, and low) in the post-course survey were organized by the likelihood (high, neutral, and low) of selecting MechE as a major. The results in **Figure 3** were used to determine that regardless of the likelihood to select MechE as a major, the majority of student respondents (54–89%, n=67–110, based on the specific modern making skill) generally had high confidence in their ability to utilize modern making skills. This new information, in combination with a previous study [13], supports attributing the high confidence in maker skills to completing the course curriculum. There is no clear trend connecting the high confidence in maker skills to students’ likelihood of pursuing a degree in the engineering field of MechE.

Figure 3: The confidence in utilizing modern making skills (CAD modeling, 3D printing, laser cutting-engraving, and physical computing) organized by likelihood of each student declaring MechE as their major. These results are from only the post-course survey.

As described, the course offered the two educational modes of textbook-based fundamentals in lecture and hands-on modern making activities in laboratory. The post-course survey was intended to assess which of these two educational modes were more influential on the likelihood of students selecting MechE as their major. To examine whether lecture or laboratory was more influential, the numerical value of responses for the question were compared. The three possible outcomes were that lecture was more influential, laboratory was more influential, or both were equally influential.

The results shown in **Figure 4** are used to determine that the majority of students, more than half of the respondents (63%, n=78), found both lecture material and laboratory material to be equally influential on their selection of a MechE as a major. The secondary influence on selection of a major was laboratory material, which was reported by over one third of the respondents (36%, n=29). It is clear that a small minority of students (8%, n=10) consider lecture material to be the most influential on their selection of MechE as a major. Although these results rank both, laboratory, and lecture as being most influential to least influential, this information alone does not reflect whether that influence is positive, negative, or neutral to the students choosing MechE as a major over other degree granting programs.

Figure 4: The influence of lecture material (textbook) or laboratory material (hands-on) on the likelihood of each student declaring MechE as their major. When the influence of lecture and laboratory were rated equally, the results were marked as both being influential. This question was only asked in the post-course survey.

The survey responses for lecture material, laboratory material, or both being influential on each student was categorized by the change in likelihood of selecting MechE as a major in **Figure 5**. At the end of the course, just over half of students (55%, n=68) had the same likelihood of selecting MechE as a major as they did at the beginning of the course. At the conclusion of the course, just under a third of respondents (28%, n=35) had increased their likelihood of declaring MechE for their major as compared to the beginning of the course. In all three cases, those responding that lecture material being the most influential were in the small minority for all three decision trajectories. These results indicate that both lecture material and laboratory material influence engineering students that are selecting their field of study. But, by considering lecture material and laboratory material independently, the hands-on activities using modern making skills was more impactful than textbook knowledge of engineering equations plus calculations.

Figure 5: The likelihood of each student declaring MechE as their major either decreased, increased, or stayed the same after completing the course. The likelihood was categorized by the influence from lecture material (textbook) or laboratory material (hands-on). When the influence of lecture and laboratory were rated equally, the results were marked as both being influential. This question was only asked in the post-course survey.

Conclusion

In summary, the combination of both textbook-based lecture and hands-on laboratory were the most influential on the students' decision to declare MechE as a major. This finding is reasonable, as the course consisted of both of these two educational modes throughout the semester. Yet of the two, making activities in laboratory set this course apart from other freshman-level science, math, and technology college courses. This is reflected in laboratory alone being more influential than lecture alone on student's decision to declare MechE as their major for their field of study in the college of engineering.

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